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EVALUATION OF THE FUNCTIONAL STATE OF PATIENTS AFTER ARTHROPLASTY WITH ANKYLOSED HIP JOINT

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ABSTRACT

Primary total hip arthroplasty was performed in 250 patients. Long-term results were studied after 12 months in 240 patients (250 cases). All patients underwent an assessment of the functional state of patients with ankylosed hip joints according to the scale we developed using a 6-point system, three parameters were assessed - pain, range of motion and walking). Summing up the scores on the parameters - pain, range of motion and walking, the results of the functional state of the hip joint were evaluated. The average score of 6-5 points directly indicates hip arthroplasty. An increase in the average score after surgical treatment compared to before surgery according to 3 criteria indicates the effectiveness of TE HJ. The treatment results in 240 (91%) patients after 12 months were studied. a good result was obtained in 224 in the main group, 122 (97.6%) patients, and 102 (88.7%) patients in the control group. A satisfactory result was obtained in 15 patients, of which 3 (2.4%) patients were obtained in the main group and 12 (10.4%) patients in the control group. An unsatisfactory result was obtained in 1 patient, of which there were no patients in the main group and the control group in 1 (1.6%) patient. Mean value in points after surgery 12 months later. In the main group, it was 11.2 points, in the control group it was 10.2 points. The results of the study indicate that total hip arthroplasty is an effective method of surgical treatment that eliminates pain and improves the patient's quality of life.

Keywords: Ankylosed hip joint, assessment of the functional state, pain, range of motion, walking, before and after surgery, score.

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**ОЦЕНКА ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ ПОСЛЕ
ЭНДОПРОТЕЗИРОВАНИЯ ПРИ АНКИЛОЗИРОВАННЫМ ТАЗОБЕДРЕННЫМ
СУСТАВЕ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Произведено первичное тотальное эндопротезирование тазобедренного сустава 250 больным. Отдалённые результаты изучены через 12 месяцев у 240 больных (250 случаев). Всем больным проведено оценка функционального состояния больных при анкилозированного ТБС по разработанный нами шкале по 6 – балльной системе оценивались три параметра-боль, объём движений и ходьба). Суммируя баллы по параметрам – боль, объём движений и ходьба оценивали результаты функционального состояния ТБС, Средний балл 6-5 баллов является прямой показаний к к эндопротезирования тазобедренного сустава. Повышение средней балле после оперативного лечения по сравнению до операции по 3 критериям, показывает об эффективности ТЭ ТБС. Изучены результаты лечения у 240 (91%) больных через 12 мес. получено хороший результат у 224 из них в основной группе у-122 (97.6%) больных, в контрольной группе у 102(88.7%) больных. Удовлетворительный результат получено у 15 больных, из них в основной группе получен у- 3(2.4%) больных, в контрольной группе у12(10.4%) больных. Неудовлетворительный результат получено у 1 больных, из них в основной группе отсутствует больных, в контрольной группе у1 (1,6%) больных. Среднее значение в баллах после операции через 12 мес. в основной группе стало 11,2 баллов, в контрольной группе составило 10,2 баллов. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют, что тотальное эндопротезирование тазобедренного сустава является эффективным методом оперативного лечения, устраняющим болевой синдром и улучшающим качества жизни больного.

Ключевые слова: Анкилозированный тазобедренный сустав, оценка функционального состояния, боль, объём движений, ходьба, до и после операции, балл.

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**ANKILOZLANGAN CHANOQ-SON BO'G'IMLARI BILAN ARTROPLASTIKADAN
SO'NG BEMORLARNING FUNKSIONAL HOLATINI BAHOLASH****ANNOTATSIYA**

250 bemorda birlamchi umumiy chanoq-son artroplastikasi o'tkazildi. Uzoq muddatli natijalar 12 oydan keyin 240 bemorda (250 ta holat) o'rganildi. Barcha bemorlar 6 balli tizim yordamida ishlab chiqilgan shkala bo'yicha ankilizatsiyalangan kalça qo'shilishi bo'lgan bemorlarning funktsional holatini baholashdan o'tkazildi, uchta parametr baholandi - og'riq, harakat oralig'i va yurish). Parametrlar bo'yicha ballarni jamlash - og'riq, harakat va yurish oralig'i, chanoq-son bo'g'imining funktsional holatining natijalari baholandi. O'rtacha 6-5 ball to'g'ridan-to'g'ri chanoq-son artroplastikasining ko'rsatkichidir. Jarrohlik muolajasidan so'ng o'rtacha ballning 3 ta mezon bo'yicha operatsiyadan oldingi holatga nisbatan ortishi TE HJ samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. 12 oydan keyin 240 (91%) bemorda davolanish natijalari o'rganildi. ularning 224 tasida asosiy guruhda 122 (97,6%) bemorda, nazorat guruhida 102 (88,7%) bemorda yaxshi natijaga erishildi. 15 nafar bemorda qoniqarli natija olindi, ulardan 3 nafari (2,4%) asosiy guruhda, 12 nafari (10,4%) nazorat guruhida olingan. 1 bemorda qoniqarsiz natija olindi, ulardan asosiy guruhda bemorlar yo'q edi, nazorat guruhida 1 (1,6%) bemorda. Operatsiyadan keyingi 12 oydan keyin ballardagi o'rtacha qiymat. asosiy guruhda 11,2 ball, nazorat guruhida 10,2 ball. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, umumiy chanoq-son artroplastikasi og'riqni yo'q qiladigan va bemorning hayot sifatini yaxshilaydigan jarrohlik davolashning samarali usuli hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ankiлоzlangan chanoq-son bo'g'imi, funktsional holatni baholash, og'riq, harakat oralig'i, yurish, operatsiyadan oldin va keyin, ball.

Introduction: Total hip arthroplasty treatment for ankylosed hip arthroplasty is a current orthopedic problem. According to the literature, there are the following surgical options for hip ankylosis: palliative (decompressive, denervating, revascularizing), stabilizing (arthrodesis), and mobilizing (biological arthroplasty, endoprosthesis). (1,2,10,14). Long-term results showed that disability after palliative interventions increased from 23% to 63%, after arthrodesis from 20% to 75% and when various interpositions were used between the ankylosed articular surfaces, up to 67%, which caused most orthopaedists to abandon these operations in favour of total endoprosthesis. (5.,8,12,17). To achieve high efficacy in hip arthroplasty and the rehabilitation of patients with ankylosed hips, various scientific studies are being conducted worldwide. Most authors are working on developing biological and non-biological antirheumatic targeted drugs and surgical techniques such as synovectomy, syncapsulectomy and stem cell therapy. (1,9,18,23) Based on those mentioned above, ankylosed hip is a non-curable disease. Therefore, in most cases, hip replacement therapy is the method of choice in ankylosed hip disease. Some authors are conducting studies to improve the models depending on the clinical and radiological variants of the disease for primary or revision (cemented or non-cemented) arthroplasty. Changes in bone mineral density (BMD) play a major role in the development of osteoporosis in ankylosed hips and negatively influence the instability of the arthroplasty. Postoperative aseptic changes in the bone tissue around the prosthesis cause periprosthetic bone resorption around the arthroplasty (12,15,16,23). Current problems are instability of the TE and fractures of the femoral component, the presence of complications, the severity of revision interventions and the prevention of complications.

The assessment of the results of hip arthroplasty using our developed scale is the initial scale, designed to quantify the results of hip arthroplasty. All patients were assessed for the functional status of patients with ankylosed hips using the 6-point system we developed and three parameters - pain, range of motion, and walking - were assessed. In order to assess the functional condition before the total hip arthroplasty, there were assessed 3 criteria (from severe pain 1 to no pain 6 points). The degree of range of motion with ankylosis in a vicious position is 1 to 200 to 300 deg. The walking condition was assessed from no walking or barely walking 1 to normal 6. When assessing the range of motion, the range of motion of flexion, extension, adduction, abduction, internal rotation and external rotation is summed up. When a patient has a fixed deformity, this is subtracted from the total. The three main parameters are summed up. These parameters were summed before surgery, the functional status of the hip was determined, and the indication for surgery was clarified. After surgical treatment, the sum of scores was summed up as good 12-10 scores, satisfactory 9-7 scores, 6 scores and below - not satisfactory. An indication for surgery was a score of 6 or below. By summing up the scores on the parameters of pain, range of motion and walking, the results of the functional state of the hip were assessed.

Research materials and methods: We followed up with 250 patients from 2010 to 2022. TBCA in the Department of Orthopaedics at RSNPMCTO. Of them: Idiopathic - 90, posttraumatic - 40 and Bechterew's disease - 120 patients. There were 90 males and 120 females. Most of the patients, 67%, were between the ages of 35 and 65. All patients underwent THA of the TPS. After surgical intervention, the functional status of patients with ankylosed hips was assessed using a scale developed by us.

Assessment of the functional status of patients with this ankylosis using a scale we have developed

Point	Pain	Movement volume	Walking
1	Severe, sleep loss	Ankylosis in a vicious position	Can't walk, or almost can't walk.
2	Severe pain while walking, the patient cannot work	Ankylosis in a functional position	Short distances only

3	Ample pain, the patient cannot do light work.	0 - 70	Walking is limited, walking for about an hour with one cane.
4	Pain after exertion disappears during rest	70 - 140	Long distances with a cane, short distances without a cane
5	With light or infrequent occurring pain, the patient can do any job.	140 - 200	Limp, but walks without a cane
6	No pain	200 - 300	Normal

We studied the severity of pain before and after surgery (Table 2).

Table 2

Pain severity before and after surgery

The table shows 66 patients with severe sleep loss before the operation in the main group

Point	Pain	Main group		Control group		Total	
		Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Severe, sleep loss	35	-	31	-	66	-
2	Severe pain while walking, the patient cannot work	80	2	73	5	153	7
3	Ample pain, the patient cannot do light work	15	10	16	9	31	19
4	Pain after exertion, disappears during rest	-	30	-	48		78
5	Light or infrequent occurring pain, the patient can do any job	-	75	-	53		128
6	No pain	-	13	-	5		18
Total		250	130	130	120	250	250
Average point		5.2	10,5	5,3	8,3		

of 35 and the control group of 31. Extreme pain while walking and inability to work were observed in 153 patients before the operation in the main group of 80 and the control group of 73 patients. Pain after the operation was observed in the main group in 2 patients and the control group in 5 patients. Moderate pain, unable to do light work, was observed in 31 patients in the main group of 15 and the control group before the operation. After the operation, 10 patients in the main group

and 9 in the control group were affected. Pain after loading, relieved at rest was not observed in both groups before the operation. Pain after operation was observed in 78 patients, 30 patients in the main group and 48 patients in the control group. Slight or occasional pains before operation, no pain before operation in both groups, after operation in 128 patients, 75 patients in the main group and 53 in the control group. No pain was observed in both group before the operation. 13 patients were observed in the main group and 5 in the control group after the operation. These figures indicate the effectiveness of our surgical treatment.

We studied the range of motion of the hip in the observed patients before and after the operation (Table 3).

Point	Movement volume	Main group		Control group treatment		Total	
		Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Ankylosis in a vicious position	30	-	35	-	65	-
2	Ankylosis in a functional position	82	-	69	-	151	-
3	0 - 70	18	20	16	25	34	45
4	70 - 140	-	55	-	53	-	108
5	140 - 200	-	50	-	40	-	90
6	200 - 300	-	5	-	2	-	7
Total	250	130	130	120	120	250	250
Average point		5,5	10,2	5.6	9,1		

The table shows that 65 patients had ankylosis in the vicious position before surgery, 30 in the main group and 35 in the control group. 151 patients had ankylosis in the functional position; 82 were in the main group and 69 were in the control group. No postoperative movements were observed in either group. 0 - 70 before operation in 34 patients, 18 in the main group, 16 patients in the control group. 45 patients were observed after the operation, 20 in the main group and 25 in the control group.

Both groups had no preoperative range of motion between 70 and 140. 108 patients were followed after surgery, 55 in the main group and 53 in the control group. Both groups had no movement volume between 140 and 200 before the operation. After the operation, 90 patients were observed, 50 in the main group and 40 in the control group. Mobility 200-300 before surgery was not available in both groups, 7 patients were observed after surgery, 5 patients in the main group, 2 patients in the control group. These figures indicate an improvement in the treatment outcome.

We studied the walking condition of patients before and after surgery (Table 4).

Table №4

Assessment of walking condition in patients with ankylosed hip joint before surgery

Point	Walking	Main group		Control group		Total	
		Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Can't walk, or almost can't walk.	30	-	28	-	58	
2	Short distances only	85	-	77	-	162	
3	Walking is limited, walking for about an hour with one cane	10	5	12	8	22	13
4	Long distances with a cane, short distances without a cane	5	56	3	55	8	111
5	Limp, but walks without a cane	-	54	-	47		101
6	Normal	-	15	-	10		25
Total	250	130	130	120	120	250	250
Average point		5,4	10,8	5,5	9,3		

The table shows that 58 patients with ankylosed hips were unable or almost unable to walk before surgery; 30 of them were in the main group and 28 in the control group. Only short-distance walking was possible in 162 patients, 85 in the main group and 77 in the control group; all patients in both groups walked after the operation. Walking restricted, one hour of walking with a walking stick before the operation was observed in 22 patients, 10 in the main group, 12 in the control group. 5 patients in the main group, 8 in the control group were observed after the operation. Long distance with cane, short distance without cane were observed in 8 patients before the operation, 5 patients in the main group, 3 patients in the control group. 11 patients were observed after the operation, 56 of them in the main group, 55 in the control group. After the operation all 101 patients were walking without cane. 54 patients were in the main group, 47 patients in the control group. All patients could not walk normally before the operation in both groups, 25 patients could walk normally after the operation, 15 patients in the main group and 10 in the control group. After surgery, the mean score increased to between 9 and 11. These values indicate the effectiveness of THA in ankylosed hips.

Here is an example of a patient from our observations (Figure 1. Patient X., age 62 years, medical history No. 250, 2016. Diagnosis: Grade IV posttraumatic coxarthrosis, left-sided fibrous ankylosis in the malpositioning unit. The patient was disturbed by severe pain even at night (2 points), no movement in the hip joint (1 point), walking with a cane, and limping (2.1 points). The total score of 5.1 points. In this case, the total score was assessed as a poor functional condition of the hip joint, which was an indication for surgery - THA of the hip joint.

Pic. 1. Before treatment

Thus, we can say that based on the results of the study, pain, range of motion and walking are good indicators of the depth of hip joint dysfunction; these indicators also indicate indications for hip arthroplasty. The functional status of patients with ankylosed hip arthroplasty was assessed using a scale we developed for pain, range of motion, and walking.

An average score of 6-5 directly indicates hip arthroplasty. An increase in the mean score after surgical treatment according to preoperative 3 criteria shows the effectiveness of our surgical treatment.

The long-term outcome was studied in 250 (100%) patients after 3 months, in 6 months and in 240 (91 %) patients after 12 months (Table 5).

Table 5.

Long-term outcome assessment of hip arthroplasty

Grade (point)	After 3 months.		After 6 months.		After 12 months	
	Main group	Control group	Main group	Control group	Main group	Control group
Good (1,4- 2,9)	121 (93,1 %)	100(83,3 %)	123 (94.6%)	103(85.8%)	122 (97.6%)	102(88.7 %)
Satisfactory 3- 4,2	8 (6,1 %)	17(14.2 %)	6(4.6%)	15(12.5%)	3(2.4%)	12(10.4%)
Unsatisfactory (4,3-5 баллов)	1 (0,8%)	3 (2,5 %)	1 (0.8%)	2(1.6%)		1(0.9%)
Average value 0 - 12 points	130 (100%) 10,8 points	120 (100%) 9,3 points	130 (100%) 11,2 points	120 (100%) 9,8	125 (100%) 11,6 points	115 (100%) 10,2 points

We studied treatment results after 3 months in 250 (100%) patients, with good results in 221 patients, 121 patients in the main group (93.1%) and 100 patients in the control group (83.3%). There were 25 patients with satisfactory results, among them 8 patients in the main group (6.1%) and 17 patients in the control group (14.2%). Unsatisfactory result in 4 patients, 1 (0.8%) in the main group and 3 (2.5%) in the control group. The mean score in the long-term follow-up before TP of the TPS was 10-12. After surgery, the mean score in the main group was 10.8 and in the control group was 9.3.

The treatment results were studied in 250 (100%) patients after 6 months. A good result was obtained in 226 patients, including in the main group - in 123 (94,6%) patients, in the control group - in 103 (85,8%) patients. A satisfactory result was obtained in 21 patients, including - 6 (4.6%) patients in the main group and 15 (12.5%) in the control group. Unsatisfactory results in 3 patients, 1 (0.8%) in the main group and 1 (0.9%) in the control group. The average score after the operation was 11.6 in the main group and 9.8 in the control group six months later.

The results of treatment were studied in 240 (100%) patients after 12 months. 225 patients received good results, including 122 (97.6%) in the main group and 102 (88.7%) in the control group. There were 15 patients with satisfactory results, 3 (2.4%) in the main group and 12 (10.4%) in the control group. Unsatisfactory results in 3 patients, including 1 (0.8%) in the main group and 2 (1.6%) in the control group. The mean score after the operation was 11.2 in the main group and 10.2 in the control group 12 months later.

These values indicate the effectiveness of total hip arthroplasty in hip arthroplasty.

Conclusions:

1. the assessment of the functional status of patients with ankylosed hips using the scale we developed is based on three parameters: pain, range of motion, and walking.

2. Increase in the average score after surgical treatment according to preoperative 3 criteria shows good effectiveness of hip replacement therapy.

3. Mean scores before treatment were 6 -5.5; after 3 months 9.3 - 10.8; after 6 months 9.8 - 11.2; after 12 months 10.2 - 11.6. These figures indicate the effectiveness of THA and faster recovery of mobility and walking in patients.

4. 12 months after the treatment results were studied - good results in the main group 97,6%, in the control group 88,7%, satisfactory in the main group 2,4%, in the control group 10,4% Unsatisfactory results in the main group 0,8%, in the control group - 1,6% of patients.

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